

A comparative study evaluating the ability of electro-bioreactors to deliver electric field for tissue engineering by finite element modelling

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INTRODUCTION: Tissue engineering provides promising alternative treatments to a variety of defects. Electric field (EF) was found ubiquitously in the biological system long ago, but its use in regulating tissue growth in vitro was popularized in past few years. A number of novel electro-bioreactors were developed recently [1, 2]. Among all, the electro-bioreactors with I-shape (design A) and L-shape (design B) electrodes are compatible with standard 6-well plate, providing an easy-to-use, inexpensive platform to study the effect of EF on cells in culture. However, their performance of delivering EF to cells remains unclear. Here, we attempted to answer the above question using finite element modelling (FEM). EF in design A and B were compared, leading to the proposal of an optimal bioreactor design (C) with rectangular shape electrodes. Design C is compatible with a standard rectangular 8-well Runc plate.

METHODS: Commercial COMSOL Multiphysics FEM software was used to simulate the A, B and C bioreactor design. The models were composed of two platinum (Pt) electrodes and one circular or rectangular main body with 3 ml cell culture media (figure 1). By using direct current, electric potential difference of 100 V/m was applied between the two electrodes. Electric insulation was applied on the outer boundary of the model. Free tetrahedral elements were used to mesh the geometry and a mesh sensitivity test was conducted to determine the optimal element size. The distributions of EF on bottom surface of culture media (cell culture area) were generated and their average values were calculated.

Fig. 1: FEA models of design A, B and C.

RESULTS: The average values of electric field on the cell culture area are shown in table 1. The EF distributions are visualized in figure 2. In terms of EF homogeneity, Electro-bioreactor with I-shape electrodes was the lowest, while the proposed design with rectangular electrodes was the highest. Although a 100 V/m electric potential difference was applied, design A only had an average EF of 63 V/m. In comparison, design B showed a higher value (85 V/m) and EF in the center region was close to 100 V/m. Design C resulted in a uniform electric field (100 V/m) throughout the model.

Table 1. Average EF values on cell culture area.

Design	A	B	C
Electric field (V/m)	63	85	100

Fig. 2: EF distribution of design A, B and C.

DISCUSSION & CONCLUSIONS: It can be concluded from the FEM predictions that the geometry of both electrode and bioreactor chamber plays an important role in delivering electric field. In order to study the effect of EF on cells in culture, it is crucial to avoid EF gradient in the experiment. Compared with electro-bioreactors with I- and L-shape electrodes, the proposed design (C) has the best uniformity of applied EF.

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